

Digital Media usage and the 2023 General Elections in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined digital media usage in the 2023 general elections in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The objectives of this study included: finding out the predominant digital media platform that Akwa Ibom electorate were exposed to election messages in the 2023 general elections; examining whether digital media used in the 2023 general elections enhanced their participation in electoral activities; determining the challenges posed by digital media in the 2023 general elections, as well as finding out whether there was disparity in the usage of digital media between urban and rural electorate in the 2023 general elections among Akwa Ibom residents. The study was anchored on the Technological Determinism Theory and Technology Acceptance Model. This study employed survey research design and a total of 400 respondents constituted the sample size drawn from the population of 2, 351, 418 registered voters in Akwa Ibom State in 2023. Results of the study revealed that exposure to election messages on digital media was high and that 81% of the electorate made use of social media platforms as the primary channels of information on the elections. A total of 62.6% of the respondents admitted digital media enhanced participation of citizens in electorate activities. However, 47.1% agreed that digital media usage abated the spread of misinformation and hate speech during the 2023 elections. The disparities in digital media usage between urban and rural electorate revealed significant inequalities, with 53% of respondents identifying location as a factor that influenced their digital engagement. The study concluded that there is a strong relationship between digital media literacy and voters' ability to identify credible election-related information. Based on the findings of the study, the study recommended that: government and stakeholders should invest in digital literacy programmes particularly in rural areas and that digital media should be utilised to facilitate interactive engagement between voters and political actors.

Keywords: Digital, Elections, Electorate, Media, Usage

Introduction

The advent of digital media has significantly improved political communication and increasingly influenced electorate's involvement in political activities. Election umpires, political parties, candidates and electorate utilise the digital media to interact, seek information and transmit information, as the case may be, without waiting to meet face-to-face. Ahmad (2017) observes that digital media fundamentally alter the relationship between the physical and social locations and a social location thereby weakening the significance of physical location in our social relationships. Also, Allen and Duru (2021) opine that through digital media, people access and share information across borders. The platforms make the world more connected and interdependent, enabling ideas, values, and information to spread quickly, often out-spacing physical and cultural borders. This has led to a change in how people communicate and create communities, as many people now form virtual communities based on interests rather than proximity. These interests can be cultural, educational, religious, economic or political, depending on the objectives and nature of such communities.

Digital media, which comprise social networking sites including WhatsApp, X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, YouTube and Instagram, as well as blogs, websites and digital news platforms, have become a vital device for electoral activities, helping users to engage in real-time communication, influence public opinion and promote political agenda. According to Suntai and Targema (2017) cited in Oladimeji (2023, p.146), the “adoption of digital media for electioneering purposes is a significant phenomenon that has transformed the interaction, communication, and sharing of information between politicians and the electorate in Nigeria and throughout the world in the twenty-first century.”

Digital media are interactive and networked technologies, such as the internet and websites (Oladimeji, 2023). Unlike traditional media, digital media convert all kinds of information into binary data, which greatly increases the density of data and makes the quantisation of information easy to realise.

In the political space, Okoro and Nwafor (2013) note that digital media are used by political aspirants to appeal to citizens, contact supporters, and they in turn contribute actively by commenting on various political aspirants' agendas and aspirations. Moreso, the use of digital media is not limited to politicians, candidates and the electorate, as election umpires like the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) also use digital media to share information with political parties, candidates and electorate. Oseni (2015) avers that starting from the point of the campaign, through voting to the collation of results and the subsequent declaration of winners by the INEC, social media, especially Facebook and X (formerly Twitter) were formidable forces in keeping the masses informed.

Several studies have also shown that political party candidates use digital media platforms to share their ideologies and philosophies, campaign tactics, and accomplishments to connect directly with the electorate. Also, WhatsApp groups have become very useful for targeted messaging and mobilisation. Similarly, political debates and candidate engagements gained prominence on platforms such as Twitter and YouTube, allowing electorate, especially the youth, to participate actively in political discourse (Ojebode & Azeez, 2022; Olayiwola, 2023).

The widespread usage of digital media in electioneering in Nigeria since 2011, which according to Okoro and Nwafor (2013), was the first test of social media use for political involvement, is not unconnected with the media's offerings of two-way communication, immediate feedback, direct interaction between citizens and candidates, real time monitoring

of public opinions and responses, coordinating of campaign activities, among other applications (Okoro & Santas, 2017). The platforms also offered a cost-effective way communication campaigns compared to traditional media such as television and newspapers. Platforms like Twitter and Facebook also amplified transparency and accountability during the elections, as citizens could share on-the-spot updates and expose malpractices.

However, despite the avalanche of benefits offered by digital media, especially as the “force that lubricates the engine room of democracy in Africa” (Borah, 2016), these innovations also come challenges. There are indications that digital media are wrongly used by some political stakeholders to foment troubles and spread fake news and disinformation. Suntai and Targema (2017) opine that although new media provide a platform to facilitate democracy in Nigeria, they are deployed as platforms to perpetuate campaigns of calumny against candidates with opposing views. Apuke and Tunca (2018) corroborate the view above, noting that social media are also used to promote propaganda and manipulate the electoral process in Nigeria and Africa in general. Supporting this position, Oyenuga (2015) believes that digital media usage during political campaigns, often turns out to be an intense and deadly weapon in the hands of political candidates, with various video releases, voice lines, feature reports, and articles, among others which is made to tarnish the image and reputation of other political candidates and individuals.

As in other states of the federation, digital media were equally used during the 2023 general elections in Akwa Ibom state. Information regarding the conduct of the election, activities of INEC, campaigns by candidates/manifestoes, and political parties’ activities were posted on social media platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter (now X) and Instagram. Others were posted on YouTube, Tiktok, Google meet, Zoom link, websites, blogs, and some in form of podcast and vlogs. However, it is not clear whether digital media usage during the 2023 general elections in Akwa Ibom State did in any way increase political participation or not. This is because the digital divide between urban and rural populations in Akwa Ibom state remains wide. Many rural voters lacked access to smartphones and stable internet connections, which must have excluded them from online political engagements. This divide further reinforced inequalities in political communication and participation. This therefore focused on examining usage of digital media during the 2023 general election in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The rapid adoption of digital media in political communication and electioneering in Nigeria has influenced voter mobilisation, campaigns, organisation, political engagement and access to campaign activities, regardless of distance. Digital technologies such as WhatsApp, Facebook, X formerly Twitter, websites, email and YouTube have provided platforms for real-time information dissemination, increased political participation and transparency. Nevertheless, their usage in elections has equally brought to the fore serious challenges that threaten the credibility, inclusiveness, and stability of Nigeria’s democracy. These digital tools have also become avenues for disseminating propaganda, hate speeches, misinformation and cyber manipulation.

Political stakeholders took undue advantage of the digital platforms to disseminate unverified, sensational, and often misleading content to influence voter perceptions. For instance, the then APC candidate for Abak/Etim Ekpo/Ika federal constituency in Akwa Ibom State, Clement Jumbo, accused his PDP opponent, Aniekan Umanah of hiring thugs to hijack ballot boxes. This, no doubt bred confusion among the electorate, eroded trust in the electoral process, and amplified tensions. Instances of manipulated videos, doctored images, and false

claims circulated widely on WhatsApp and Facebook, further polarising the political atmosphere.

Again, another critical issue amplified by the usage of digital media in elections is the digital divide, which limits the benefits of digital media to urban and tech-savvy populations while leaving out those in the rural communities. In Akwa Ibom State, many residents of rural communities lack reliable internet connectivity, others cannot afford smartphones, and technological literacy remains a serious threat to political inclusivity. This marginalisation creates an imbalance in political participation, as voters in rural areas are left out of the digital political discourse and are unable to access critical election-related information.

While digital platforms offer rich opportunities to facilitate political engagements, their misuse threatens the integrity of democratic processes. Therefore, this study sought to examine the extent to which digital media were used during the elections in Akwa Ibom State, and their influence on the mobilisation and political participation of the electorate.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

- i. What were the digital media platforms that Akwa Ibom electorate were exposed to election messages during the 2023 general elections?
- ii. To what extent did the use of digital media enhance Akwa Ibom electorate's participation in electoral activities during the 2023 general elections?
- iii. What were the challenges posed by digital media use during the 2023 general elections among Akwa Ibom electorate?
- iv. Were there any disparity between urban and rural electorate's exposure to digital media during the 2023 general elections in Akwa Ibom State?

Literature Review

Digital media have come to stay in our world, and everything seems to go the digital way. This form of media is so pervasive that people who still utilise the analogue media are seen as archaic, old school or out of touch with the real world. It is assumed that the mass diffusion of personal computers, smartphones, tablets and other mobile technologies, and an accompanying near-ubiquitous connectivity, have entered into the daily lives of ordinary people.

Digital media are media encoded in machine-readable formats. They include media that can be created, viewed, distributed, modified, listened and preserved on a digital electronic device. Smith (2013) opines that digital media are any data represented with a series of digits and broadcast through screens. These include audio, text, video and graphics that are transmitted over the internet, for viewing on the internet (Rayburn, 2012). They are any kind of media which can be processed, analysed, stored and distributed by electronic digital machines and devices. Electronic digital machines are media which covers content and promotions delivered through digital platforms including electronic media, mobile phones, computers, podcasts, applications, among others. They are various contents created, distributed and consumed through digital devices and internet based platforms. Digital media are also seen as devices that can be used to access digital contents such as smart phones, tablets, Personal Digital Assistants (PDA) and others. They encompass communication tools like email, websites, social media, blogs, mobile applications, video-sharing platforms, among others.

Oladimeji (2023) avers that digital media comprise social networking sites such as Facebook, YouTube, WhatsApp, X (formerly Twitter), and Instagram, as well as blogs,

websites and digital news platforms. They are web-based technologies that are interactive and networkable, such as the internet and websites. Unlike traditional media, digital media is transmitted as digital data, and it involves digital cables or satellites, sending binary signals — 0s and 1s — to devices that translate them into audio, video, graphics, text, and more. Anytime you use your computer, tablet, or cellphone, opening web-based systems and apps. (Yu, 2022).

The beauty of digital media lies in their characteristics of interactivity, immediacy and personalized communication. Hence, users can comfortably create, share and engage with contents in real time. It facilitates a two-way information flow between content creator and consumers, creating a participatory culture (Jenkins, 2006), where users actively engage in discussions, share opinions and co-create contents (Kim, 2024). Supporting Kim's view, Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) opine that digital media facilitate direct interaction, enabling real-time feedback and dialogue. Jenkins avers that participatory culture amplified by the digital media challenges traditional notions of passive consumption, positioning audiences as co-creators in the media landscape. For instance, digital media platforms like Twitter enable real-time conversations on global issues, while YouTube allows users to comment on and share videos, creating a dynamic flow of information and ideas. They equally provide instant (immediate) access to information on the global stage as it is being shared (breaking news), irrespective of geographical boundaries. This perhaps, explains why digital media are increasingly used in almost every sector, including media, education, entertainment, business, politics, etc. The platforms have created a paradigm shift in the communication world, especially in the way information is created, shared and consumed. Preston (2024) notes that digital media has changed the way we learn, entertain, publish and interact with one another on a daily basis.

Digital Media Use in the 2023 General Elections

The 2023 general elections in Akwa Ibom state is one that digital media was greatly used by political parties, candidates, INEC, and other stakeholders. No doubt, there is a rapid increase in the use of digital media for political communication, engagement and mobilisation, and this has affected the way people engage with information, communicate and express their opinions. According to Igbinedion and Ajisebiyawo (2023), the role of digital media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and WhatsApp has grown exponentially in political discourse, as these platforms have emerged as powerful tools for political communication, enabling candidates and parties to reach a wide audience instantly. Social media users tweeted over 12.4 million tweets about elections over the period and 216, 000 Facebook users interacted with contents on popular public pages related to the elections (Luckscheiter, 2022). In line with this report, Igbinedion and Ajisebiyawo (2023) aver that the same scenario unfolded in the build-up to the 2023 general elections in Nigeria. They added that the three major presidential candidate- Peter Obi, Atiku Abubakar and Bola Ahmed Tinubu, significantly increased their followership on Facebook and Twitter, with hashtags directly related to candidates trend on local Twitter and Facebook almost daily.

Shadrach and Apuke (2019) note that digital media allow political candidates and parties to directly communicate with a large audience. This submission is not unconnected to the viral nature of digital media which enables messages to spread rapidly, amplifying their reach and impact. Again, Stier (2018) cited in Agbim, *et al.* (2023) opines that digital media platforms offer sophisticated targeted options, allowing candidates to tailor their campaign messages to specific demographics, locations or interests. This is in addition to the fact that digital media platforms provide a two-way communication pattern, which allows candidates to have real-time interaction with the electorate. Prior to the 2023 general elections in Nigeria,

almost all major campaigns were live-streamed, and candidates' messages and that of the election umpires were inundated on all major digital platforms common to Nigerians. This is so because political stakeholders have come to the realisation that digital media increasingly provide platforms for awareness creation on political issues and mobilisation with ease and low cost. For instance, Twitter allows political candidates, parties and activists to disseminate information about their policies, campaign events and achievements.

Oelsner and Heimrich (2015) are of the opinion that digital media are recent e-campaigning tools which allow political aspirants to speak to voters at once in more personalised, responsive and dialogue manner, enhancing the connection between citizens and candidates. This means that the use of digital media during the 2023 general elections was as a result of the fact that platforms appeal to citizens, and give politicians the advantage of keeping in touch with electorate and supporters always. As it stands, almost all political parties, civil society organisations, electoral bodies (states and national) and political parties' candidates have digital presence. This is due to the pervasive nature of digital media and their impact in political discourse.

Theoretical Framework

The research was anchored on the theories of Technological Determinism Theory and Technology Acceptance Model. The Technological Determinism Theory (TDT) propounded by American Economist, Thorstein Veblen in 1962 and it revolves around the proposition that technology in any given society defines its nature. According to Macaulay *et al.* (2013), technology is viewed as the driving force of culture in a society and it determines its course of history. Under this theory media technologies shape how individuals in a society think, feel, and act, as well as how a society operates, as we progress through technological epochs (Oladimeji, 2023). Iwok *et al.* (2024) assert that the technological determinism theory is a reductionist theory that assumes that a society's technology progresses by following its own internal logic of efficiency while determining the development of the social structure and cultural values.

This theory claims that technology is the dynamic factor at the root of societal changes and has strong and direct impacts on the development of social structures, cultural values, and individual behaviours. According to Ezeagwu (2016), huge societal changes come out of technological changes, which eventually compel people and institutions to adapt themselves and develop new ways of thinking, behaving, and organizing (Ezeagwu, 2016). Technological Determinism Theory assumes that technology is a driving force for most features of a society and, subsequently, social and cultural elements are "the consequences" of technological changes. At the same time, this theory presumes that technology has some sort of autonomous agency driving processes of change and that it follows a predictable path of development in a linear fashion.

The concept of technological determinism is considered appropriate for this study because the theory asserts that digital media can influence the way people engage in political communication. This is so because the theory believes that technology is a driving force in today's world, and is so pervasive that it has greater influence on people's day-to-day living. Going by this assumption, it can be presumed that political parties, candidates, politicians and citizens adopted digital media during the 2023 general elections because of its ubiquitous nature and capacity to drive political change.

The second theory of Technology Acceptance model (TAM) was developed by Fred Davis in 1989, and it is one of the most widely used models to explain user acceptance behavior. In other words, the theory helps to explain how users come to accept and use technology. This theory is used to predict user acceptance of new technology based on two key beliefs- Perceived Usefulness (PU) and the Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU). The PU is the belief

that a technology will help improve performance, while the PEOU is the belief that a technology is easy to learn and operate. According to Ma (2004), PU and PEOU form an end-user's beliefs on a technology and therefore predict his or her attitude toward the technology, which in turn predicts its acceptance.

The theory postulates that the acceptance of technology is predicted by the user's behavioural intention, which is predominantly determined by the perception of technology usefulness in performing the task and perceived ease of its use. This means that using a particular technology should enhance performance, be free of effort and this will facilitate the likelihood of using the technology.

However, this theory has been criticized though it is widely used and applied, on the grounds over-simplicity, limited predictive power, lack of social and cultural context and western bias, among other.

Relating the theory to the study, the theory helps to explain why electorate in Akwa Ibom State chose platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, Tiktok, Instagram to access, share or engage with election related information during the 2023 general elections in Nigeria. If electorate perceived digital media platforms as useful for timely election updates, they are more likely to adopt them.

Research Method

This study employed the survey research design using a structured questionnaire as instrument for data collection. The population for this study was made up of the total number of registered voters for the 2023 general elections in Akwa Ibom State, which stood at 2,357,418 according to the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC, 2023). These voters formed the broad base from which opinions about digital media usage in the elections could be drawn. The sample size for this study was calculated using the Yamane's formula propounded by Taro Yamane in 1967 and cited in Obasi (2013, p.43) as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where,

n= Sample size

N= population of the study

e= Error limit (being 0.01 or 0.05)

1 = Unity or constant value.

$$n = \frac{2357418}{1+ 2357418 (0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{2357418}{1+ 2357418 \times 0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{2357418}{1+5893.545}$$

$$n = \frac{2357418}{5893.545}$$

n= 400.

Therefore, the sample size for the first population of the study will be 400.

A multistage sampling technique was employed in selecting participants from the first population of the study. This approach combines different sampling methods to ensure that the sample accurately reflects the characteristics of the larger population.

Akwa Ibom State comprises 31 Local Government Areas, grouped into three senatorial districts, namely Akwa Ibom North West (covering 10 Local Government Areas), Akwa Ibom North East (comprising 9 Local Government Areas), and Akwa Ibom South (encompassing 12 Local Government Areas). The state was first clustered along these three senatorial districts. From each district, one Local Government Area was selected using a cluster sampling approach. Selection was guided by factors such as population size, accessibility, and active participation during the 2023 general elections. The selected Local Government Areas were Abak from Akwa Ibom North West Senatorial District, Uyo from Akwa Ibom North East Senatorial District, and Eket from Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District.

The researcher proportionately surveyed respondents from the three selected Local Government Areas based on their population sizes. Uyo, being the most urbanised and densely populated, had 150 respondents; Eket, with a moderate population, had 130 respondents; while Abak, with a smaller population, had 120 respondents. This distribution brought the total number of respondents to 400, which constituted the sample size for the study. Out of the 400 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 39 copies were not completed properly and were discarded leaving 361 valid copies. This accounted for 90.25% rate of return.

Data Presentation

Table 1: Responses on the digital media platform respondents used most for accessing election messages during the 2023 general elections

Options	Frequency	Percentages
Social media platforms	292	81
Online discussion forums	27	7
Blogs	7	2
Microblogging platforms	21	6
Podcasting platforms	11	3
Others	3	1
Total	361	100

The data presented in Table I reveals that a significant majority of 292 respondents, accounting for 81% relied on social media platforms as their primary source for accessing election messages during the 2023 general elections. This highlights the dominant role of social media in shaping public discourse around elections.

Table 2: Responses on whether digital media influence respondents' decision to participate in the 2023 general elections?

Options	Frequency	Percentages
Yes	226	62.6
No	18	5
Undecided	117	32.4
Total	361	100

The data presented in Table 2 above indicates that a substantial majority of respondents believe that digital media significantly influences their decision to participate in the 2023 general elections. A total of 266 respondents representing 62.6% affirm that digital media plays a role in their decision-making process. This overwhelming inclination toward the influence of digital media suggests its critical role in shaping electoral engagement and highlights the importance of online platforms in informing and mobilizing voters.

Table 3: Responses on the challenges respondents encountered while using digital media during the 2023 general elections

Options	Frequency	Percentages
Misinformation and fake news	170	47.1
Internet connectivity issues	23	6.37
Hate speech and cyberbullying	67	18.56
Difficulty in verifying credible sources	63	17.45
Other	38	10.52
Total	361	100

The data presented in Table 3 reflects the challenges faced by respondents while using digital media during the 2023 general elections. From the computation above, 170 respondents accounting 47.1% claimed that digital media encouraged misinformation and fake news while hate speech and cyberbullying accounted for 18.56% of the contents of digital media among others.

Table 4: Responses on whether respondents' location influenced their usage of digital media during the 2023 general elections?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	135	37.4
No	142	39.3
Undecided	84	23.3
Total	361	100

The data presented in Table 4 indicates that 142 respondents representing 39.3% do not believe that their location influenced their usage of digital media during the 2023 general

elections while 84 respondents accounting for 23.3% were undecided on whether that their location did have impact on their digital media usage in 2023 general elections.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study were discussed based on the research questions raised.

RQ1: What digital media platforms were the Akwa Ibom electorate exposed to during the 2023 general elections?

The findings regarding the predominant digital media platforms utilised by Akwa Ibom electorate to access election messages during the 2023 general elections revealed that 81% of the respondents used social media platforms as their primary sources for election messages. This finding corroborates Bassey (2020) that the social media platforms were popular especially among the youths in the 2019 general elections.

RQ2: To what extent did the use of digital media enhance Akwa Ibom electorate participation in electoral activities in the 2023 general elections?

Findings from the data presented Table 2 indicate that a total of 62.6 % of the respondents actively engaged with election-related content through various digital platforms, signifying a marked increase in participation levels. This engagement is suggestive of citizens seeking not just information, but also a platform to voice their opinions and concerns during the elections. The active participation through sharing posts and commenting indicates a transformation from passive consumption of information to a more engaged user role in democratic processes. The direct nature of social media platforms allows users to exchange information rapidly, stimulating a collective dialogue among local voters. The finding supports earlier assertion by Bassey (2020) that as an interactive and relational communication tools, social media have exerted enormous impact on political sensitization and mobilization of citizens. The capacity of digital media to stimulate informed discussions elevates the overall involvement of voters, encouraging them to partake in elections not merely as perfunctory tasks but as informed and meaningful choices.

RQ3: What were the challenges posed by digital media use in the 2023 general elections among Akwa Ibom electorate?

From Table 3 above, 170 respondents representing 47.1% admitted the major challenge posed by digital media use during the 2023 general elections among electorate in Akwa Ibom State was misinformation and fake news. Others were cyberbullying and hate speech, difficulties in verifying credible sources, and varying levels of difficulty with internet connectivity. This result corroborates with the assertion by Junk (2019) that the ability to discern credible sources from misinformation is indispensable for meaningful engagement in democratic processes given the prevalence of confusion and misinformation spread frequently on the social media.

RQ4: Were there any disparity in the usage of digital media between urban and rural electorate in the 2023 general elections among Akwa Ibom electorate?

Disparities in digital media usage between urban and rural electorate in the 2023 general elections among Akwa Ibom electorate were insignificant. Computation on Table revealed 142 respondents representing 39.3% did not believe that there existed disparity between urban and rural electorate in the usage of digital media while 135 respondents accounting 37.4% agreed that there was disparity. This mere non- disparity signals wide spread of technology blurring the geographical lines between urban and rural location in terms of access to technology and information dissemination in the context of electoral participation.

The evidence gathered suggests that geography did not play a substantial role in shaping digital media usage during elections within Akwa Ibom State. Urban voters and rural electorate exhibited greater engagement with digital media.

Conclusion

The examination of digital media usage during the 2023 general elections in Akwa Ibom State has provided valuable empirical evidence on the extent and nature of digital media engagement in the electoral process. The study concluded that digital media platforms were widely used, with a significant majority of respondents interacting with election-related content online. This confirms the growing centrality of digital media in informing the electorate, shaping political discourse, and influencing electoral participation in contemporary Nigerian elections.

The study further inferred that digital media platforms particularly social media such as Facebook- served as strategic tools for political parties and candidates in disseminating campaign messages and mobilising voters.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Given the predominance of social media in disseminating electoral information, political actors and campaign strategists should focus on Facebook and other popular platforms to reach a wider audience. Targeted online campaigns can significantly influence voting decisions and enhance electoral participation.
- ii. To enhance electoral participation, digital media should be utilised to facilitate interactive engagement between voters and political actors. This can be achieved through live streaming, online debates, and social media contests that encourage citizens to participate in the electoral process.
- iii. To mitigate the challenges posed by digital media use, such as misinformation and hate speech, stakeholders should promote media literacy among voters. This can be achieved through public awareness campaigns, workshops, and online resources that equip citizens with the skills to critically evaluate online information.
- iv. To enhance voters' ability to identify credible election-related information, government agencies, electoral bodies, and civil society organisations should implement comprehensive digital media literacy programmes across all sections of Akwa Ibom State, especially those in rural areas, with the skills to critically evaluate online content, detect misinformation, and verify credible sources.

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